

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

**D5.8 - Reports on joint exchange
activities experiences**

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Executive Summary

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector. The improvements in the multi-level governance and the developed energy data visualization will be designed and implemented together with three regions: Girona region in Spain (DDGI), Zlín region in the Czech Republic (EAZK) and Crete Island in Greece (RDFC).

This document (deliverable 5.8 “Reports on joint exchange activities”) provides an overview of the activities organized with the seven regions following the development of the project and their evaluation. One site visit has been organized in each pilot region. The definition of the programme was based on the results of the need survey (cf. D5.7) and in collaboration with the follower regions.

This report is composed of an introduction followed by a general description of the T5.3 Joint exchange activities. Then, more details are given on the organization and programme of each site visit together with the results of the satisfaction survey and pictures. In conclusion, we reflect on the site visit activities and organization in a more general manner and propose some best practices to replicate in other EU projects. The main recommendations are to involve the participants at an early stage of development of the programme, to not underestimate the matchmaking process and to properly define the duration of the visit. We also remind that site visits and replication activities are key to accelerate the uptake of the EU green transition. In-person and networking activities lead to new partnerships, potential new cooperations and therefore strengthen the international collaboration.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
BSRAEM	Black Sea Agency for Regional Energy Management
CRES	Centre for renewable energy sources and saving foundation
DDGI	Diputació de Girona
EU	European Union
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
RDFCM	Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The ePLANET project is now in its last phase, focusing on the transfer and expansion of its results. This stage, during which most of the WP5 Replication and Networking activities have been organized, aims to maximize the adoption of the ePLANET solutions by a wider audience, by connecting and institutionalizing the clustering networks, scaling up the project outcomes to the whole pilot regions, and maximizing its replicability to other regions at the national and EU level. This step is key in ensuring the sustainability of ePLANET tools beyond the project duration. The different activities widen the impact of the project and foster the institutionalization of multi-level networks and working groups.

As part of task 5.3 working on the EU replicability, a special focus has been put on the joint exchange activities between the three pilot regions and the seven follower regions. In addition to their participation in the Stakeholders Forums (more detailed reporting in the D5.2 to be submitted in M36), one site visit has been organized in each pilot region. All these activities have been shaped and designed to include the needs and interests of the follower regions mostly based on the results of the need survey (cf. D5.7) and meetings.

The objective of this report is to give an overview of the joint exchange activities, to describe their implementation and draw conclusions. To do so, it includes the results of an evaluation questionnaire that has been completed by the follower regions but also our pilot partners. Furthermore, to give a better impression of how the site visits took place, we included some pictures. Finally, this report is also an opportunity to reflect on the organization of site visit activities and to conclude with some best practices.

After this introduction, you will find a more detailed description of the “sub-task 5.3.3 joint exchange activities” followed by a description of each site visit programme, including the evaluation of the activities and some pictures.

2 Joint exchange activities (Task 5.3.3)

2.1 Task description

The joint exchange activities task foresees the development of bilateral peer capacity-building activities, carried out in the form of physical visits, where the follower region and the associated pilot partner meet.

The activities foreseen at the beginning of the project were the following:

- One study visit (up to 2 persons, up to 2 days) from one follower region to the ePLANET joint exchange partner region to learn more about best practices in place and to exchange experience;
- Remote (phone, mail, Webinar) support from ePLANET experts to the follower region;
- Joint evaluation of the results and of the process of the exchange;
- Promotion at European level of the regions' commitment to work and implement a collaboration model on sustainable energy with local authorities.
- One visit of ePLANET experts (2 persons, up to 2 days) to the follower region to provide technical support if requested;

To better implement and design these different activities, we used the results of the follower regions' need survey conducted earlier in the project and which results are displayed in deliverable 5.7 (D5.7). In the annexes, you can find the summary table of the activities suggested based on the need survey.

Ultimately, during the project, one study visit was organized in each pilot region, support was provided through the support@eplanet2020.eu address and social media posts showcased the follower regions' ePLANET journey until the site visits. No expert visit was requested from the follower regions but we still decided to integrate the content suggested in D5.7 either in the site visits or in Stakeholder Forums. Finally, a satisfaction survey was circulated to the participants of the site visits to gather their feedback on the organization and activities. The results for each visit are detailed in the next section.

2.2 Site visits

Before diving into each site visit programme and activities, it is important to recall that the twinning of the regions was also based on the results of the needs survey (cf. table 14, D5.7).

In addition to the needs survey results, to better shape the agenda to the needs and interests of the follower regions and to include them in the organization of the visit, we facilitated three preparation meetings, one for each region. In the next sections, you will find the description of each visit, the results of the satisfaction survey and some pictures.

2.2.1 Crete site visit

In the scope of ePLANET project and based on the results of a needs survey, we matched Crete pilot site to the following regions: the municipality of Fyli and the Regional Development Fund of the Central Macedonia (RDFCM) region, both in Greece.

In the context of this matching, the two follower regions have been invited to join a site visit taking place in Crete on the 12th and 13th of March 2024. The visit was open to up to two persons from each region.

During these days, they had the opportunity to meet officers from the Regional Development Fund of Crete (RDFC), exchange experiences, and learn about best practices in the region. In the next section, you will find the final agenda of this site visit. It was elaborated in collaboration with the follower regions to best match their needs and interests.

The participants from the follower regions were the following: Chrysanthi Kiskini and Kyriaki Kissa from the RDFCM and Chrysoula Kourasi from the municipality of Fyli.

2.2.1.1 Programme

ePLANET - Agenda Crete site visit		2 / 2
AGENDA		
Monday, 11TH of March 2024		
21:30	Welcome dinner	APIRI - Greek Eatery Agion Deka 5 &, Kayambi Heraklion
Tuesday, 12th of March 2024		
09:00	Welcome coffee Presentation of RDFC work on ePLANET project activities	RDFC premises Megaro Handax, Efodou 3 & Mahis Kritis 2 nd floor
11:00	Departure for Minoan Energy Community	Arkalohori Municipality of Minoa Pediados
11:50	Katerina Sfakianaki (CRES) Presentation for e-PLANET & re-MODULEES, H2020 projects	
12:15	Mr Charalampos Giannopoulos (President of MEC) Crete Valey and other Minoan Energy Community's projects	
14:30	Lunch	Haralabakis Winery Avli, Arkalohori
Wednesday, 13th of March 2024		
9:00	Meeting with Mr Nikolaos Xylouris (Deputy Regional Governor for Environment)	RoC premises Markou Mousourou 15, Heraklion
10:00	Meeting with Mr Yannis Anastasakis (Deputy Regional Governor for Climate Change) Mrs Ermyoni Gialiti (Regional GIS platform)	RoC premises Eleftherias Square
11:00	Departure for Rethymno	Rethymno
12:30	Meeting with Mr. Angelos Malas (Deputy Mayor) and Staff of the Municipal Technical Service	Town hall Address
14:30	Lunch	Othonas Tavern Plateia Titou Petychaki 27
16:00	Closing/ travel back to Heraklion	
Transport between the locations will be done by car/mini van.		

Figure 2-1 Agenda Crete site visit

2.2.1.2 Satisfaction survey results

We gathered three answers for the Crete site visit. You can find the results in the table below.

Table 2-1 Satisfaction survey results - Crete

What did you like about the site visit?	The visit was well organized and especially the presentations were all very useful. Moreover, the study visits were very informative and the organizations that we visited provided with lot of input.	The presentations and the interaction during the visit between all the participants.	I was a great opportunity to find out how a Greek Region is paving the way toward climate neutrality
How did you or your organization benefit from the site visit? What is your main learning?	Many good practices that we can disseminate them to our stakeholders	Since we met related organizations to ours, we came familiar on how they implement their practices and how they interact with the regional ecosystem.	Very well structured and organized. Very interactive exchanges of experience and best practices.
Are you satisfied with your involvement in the organization of the site visit and the possibility of shaping it to your needs?	Yes	Yes	Yes
What could have been done to improve the site visit? What lessons can we learn from this experience?		Everything was well organized	It has a 2 days very intensive visit. If we had more time, we could have visited other best practices too. I have learned that even in the bureaucratic Greek public sector, active and inspired politicians and public servants can really make the difference

What is your general impression of the site visit you participated in? (Rating 1-5)	5	5	5
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2.2.1.3 Impressions

Figure 2-2 Crete visit - RDFC premises

Figure 2-3 Crete visit - Meeting with the Regional Governor

Figure 2-4 Crete visit - Rethymno

Figure 2-5 Crete visit - Minoan

2.2.2 Girona site visit

In the scope of ePLANET project and based on the results of a needs survey, we matched Girona pilot site to the following regions: the Intermunicipal community of Tâmega e Sousa in Portugal, the South East Energy Agency of Ireland and Baix Llobregat County Council in Spain.

In the context of this matching, the three follower regions have been invited to join a site visit taking place in Girona on the 15th and 16th of April 2024. The visit was open to up to two persons from each region.

During these days, they had the opportunity to meet officers from Diputació de Girona (DDGI), exchange experiences, and learn about best practices in the region. In the next section, you will find the agenda for this site visit. It was elaborated in collaboration with the follower regions to match their needs and interests best.

The participants from the follower regions were the following: Mário Júlio and Maria Alves from the inter-municipal community of Tâmega e Sousa, Dewi Vliexs from the South East Energy Agency and Oscar Miquel Sicília from the Consell Comarcal del Baix Llobregat.

2.2.2.1 Programme

ePLANET - Agenda Girona site visit		2 / 3
AGENDA:		
15 th and 16 th of April 2024		
First day - 15th of April		
Morning	Travel and arrival to Girona	
10:00	Pick-up Point Barcelona-El Prat Airport	Mario and Maria (Tamega e Sousa)
10:30	Pick-up Point Barcelona Sants Train Station	Gerard (CIMNE) Oscar and Enric (Consell Comarcal Baix Llobregat) Xevi (DdGi)
12:30	Pick-up Pont Girona Hotel Carlemany	Dewi and Michael (South East Energy Agency) Nadège (FEDARENE)
13:00	Welcome by Marc Mari (Cap d'Àrea Medi Ambient)	Centre Cívic La Fàbrica (Celrà) Carretera de Juià, 46, 17460 Celrà, Girona, Spain
13:30	Lunch	
15:00	District Heating Projects by Jesús Teixidor (Suno)	Ajuntament de Celrà Sala de Plens
16:00	Site visit: Energy Efficiency - Building renovation and Photovoltaic Installation and Biomass Boilers	Centre Cívic La Fàbrica (Celrà) Carretera de Juià, 46, 17460 Celrà, Girona, Spain
19:00	Accommodation	Hotel El Convent de Begur Carretera de la Platja del Racó, 2 17255 Sa Riera, Girona
20:00	Dinner	
Day 2 - 16th of April		
09:00	Welcome Xavier Turró (Regidor Medi Ambient Begut)	Espai Mas de'n Pinc Passeig Carmen Amaya, 12 · 17255 Begur
9:30	ePLANET platform demo by Gerard Laguna (CIMNE)	
ePLANET GA nº 101032450		

Figure 2-6 Agenda Girona site visit 1

ePLANET - Agenda Girona site visit		3 / 3
10:30	Coffe Break	
11:00	Site visit: Biomass Boilers	Escola Pavelló Begur
13:30	Lunch	Restaurant Es Castell Hotel Classic Hotel Classic Begur Pi i Ralló, 3
15:00	Closing	17255 Begur, Girona
15:30	Travel back	

Transport between the locations will be done with DdGi bus.

Figure 2-7 Agenda Girona site visit 2

2.2.2.2 Satisfaction survey results

We gathered two answers for the Girona site visit. You can find the results in the table below.

Table 2-2 - Satisfaction survey results - Girona

What did you like about the site visit?	The opportunity to see how other regions are progressing in the field of energy transition and the explanations in the technical visits.	The exchange of experiences with different realities, and contact in the field and with different forms of braiding.
How did you or your organization benefit from the site visit? What is your main learning?	The future implementation of software where data is shared and worked in a coordinated manner.	The way in which entities of similar size and responsibilities struggle with problems and challenges that are very similar to the ones we struggle with. Check on site different approaches to the same problems. Intermunicipal and municipal management of the use of community funds aimed at energy efficiency.
Are you satisfied with your involvement in the organization of the site visit and the possibility of shaping it to your needs?	Yes	Yes
What could have been done to improve the site visit? What lessons	The organization of the visit was perfect. The lesson I learned is the need to all work with the same	In general, the visit was very well organized, perhaps it could have been improved with longer duration.

can we learn from this experience?	database organized and adapted to the SECAPs.	
What is your general impression of the site visit you participated in? (Rating 1-5)	5	4

2.2.2.3 *Impressions*

Figure 2-8 Girona visit - Celrà

Figure 2-9 Girona site visit - Centre Civic

Figure 2-10 Girona visit - Begur

2.2.3 Zlín site visit

In the scope of ePLANET project and based on the results of a needs survey, we matched Zlín pilot site to the following regions: the Romanian Agency for Energy Efficiency and Environmental Protection and Black Sea Agency for Regional Energy Management (BSRAEM) of Bulgaria.

In the context of this matching, the two follower regions have been invited to join a site visit taking place in Zlín on the 23th and 24th of April 2024. The visit was open to up to two persons from each region.

During these days they got the opportunity to meet officers from the Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK), exchange experiences, and learn about best practices in the region. On the next section, you will find the agenda of this site visit. It was elaborated in collaboration with the follower regions to best match their needs and interests.

The participants from the follower regions were the following: Ion Dogeanu and Dragos Dragusin from the Romanian Agency for Energy Efficiency and Environmental Protection and Todor Tonev and his colleague from BSRAEM.

2.2.3.1 Programme

DRAFT AGENDA	
Day 1 - Tuesday 23/04/2024	Speakers:
Morning	
Welcome Presentation of ePLANET project and results Presentation of Energy Transition in the Czech Republic and the Zlín Region Energy agency of the Zlín Region and its role in energy transition of the Zlín Region Knowledge sharing on energy communities (preparation/introduction of the field trip)	Tomáš Perutka (EAZK) Nadège Seguel (FEDARENE) Gerard Laguna (CIMNE) Jan Vidomus (EAZK) Tomáš Perutka (EAZK) All participants
Afternoon	
<u>Hostětín field trip</u>	Radim Machů - energy manager & local energy projects coordinator
Day 2 - Wednesday 24/04/2024	Speakers:
Morning	
Showcase and testing of the ePLANET platform Preparation/introduction of the field trip: Best practices/knowledge sharing on Energy Action Plans Best practices/knowledge sharing on PV potential of public buildings	Gerard Laguna (CIMNE) Jan Vidomus (EAZK) All participants
Afternoon	
City tour in city of Zlín following the best practices projects on Energy efficiency and RES installations	All participants

Figure 2-11 Zlín visit - Agenda

2.2.3.2 Satisfaction survey results

One week after the site visit (when drafting this report), we gathered one answer for the Zlín site visit. You can find the results in the table below.

Table 2-3 - Satisfaction survey results - Zlín

What did you like about the site visit?	The meaningful program and the professionalism of the responsible people on the visited sites
How did you or your organization benefit from the site visit? What is your main learning?	Always good people, local leaders, make the difference.
Are you satisfied with your involvement in the organization of the site visit and the possibility of shaping it to your needs?	Yes
What could have been done to improve the site visit? What lessons can we learn from this experience?	I don't have any reco here.
What is your general impression of the site visit you participated in? (Rating 1-5)	5

2.2.3.3 Impressions

Figure 2-12 Zlín visit - Hostětín district heating

Figure 2-13 Zlín visit - ePLANET showcase

Figure 2-14 Zlín site visit- PV

Figure 2-15 Zlín visit - Slavičín

Figure 2-16 Zlín visit - Hostětín

2.2.4 Results of the satisfaction survey for organizers

In order to be able to draw more complete feedback on the organization of site visits and draw conclusions for future events, we asked the organizers to complete the satisfaction survey. You will see the results in the next sections.

2.2.4.1 Crete site visit - Feedback from the organizers

Two persons from the organizing team responded to the short questionnaire from the Crete pilot.

Table 2-4 - Crete site visit - Organiser's feedback

What did you like about the site visit?	Hosting colleagues and meeting to exchange experiences	I liked the interaction between the project partners.
How did you or your organization benefit from the site visit? What is your main learning?	How local authorities can find many different ways to promote energy transition based on their assets or their identical problems.	We have learned new things about the project
What could have been done to improve the site visit? What lessons can we learn from this experience?	Expand it for one more day.	A more specific agenda would have offered wider knowledge of the project goal
What is your general impression of the site visit you participated in? (Rating 1-5)	5	5

2.2.4.2 Girona site visit - Feedback from the organizers

From the Girona pilot, the main person in charge of the organization of the visit responded to the short questionnaire.

Table 2-5 - Girona site visit - Organizer's feedback

What did you like about the site visit?	I really liked meeting energy efficiency technicians from other regions of Europe to learn how they work and to share their knowledge.
How did you or your organization benefit from the site visit? What is your main learning?	Thanks to this experience, Diputació de Girona has been able to give visibility to the energy efficiency actions carried out in different municipalities.
What could have been done to improve the site visit? What lessons can we learn from this experience?	I would have liked the follower regions to also present to us the actions they are doing in terms of energy efficiency to deepen the exchange of knowledge
What is your general impression of the site visit you participated in? (Rating 1-5)	5

2.2.4.3 Zlín site visit - Feedback from the organizers

From the Zlín pilot, the main person in charge of the organization of the visit responded to the short questionnaire.

Table 2-6 - Zlín site visit - Organizer's feedback

What did you like about the site visit?	As a organizing body, we liked the approach of following regions and their interest in a fruitful and successful visit both from professional and friendly point of view.
How did you or your organization benefit from the site visit? What is your main learning?	The visit helped to strengthen international relationship our agency is trying to maintain which leads to many positive side effects, for instance to developing new international projects based on a common experience and interests.
What could have been done to improve the site visit? What lessons can we learn from this experience?	From the point of view of the organizer, we just hope the site visit met the expectation of following regions and we hope to maintain the new relationship also in the future.
What is your general impression of the site visit you participated in? (Rating 1-5)	5

3 Conclusions

Site visits and replication activities are key to accelerating the uptake of the EU green transition in a wide range of European regions. They allow regions that were not primarily involved in the project to get deep insights and first-hand experience from project partners and benefit from ePLANET outcomes. The events inspired the participants to work on replicating the best practices and take full advantage of lessons learnt within the ePLANET pilot regions. The in-person exchange and networking opportunities proved to be especially fruitful which is reflected in the feedback from participants and organizers. New partnerships and potential new cooperations will strengthen the international collaboration.

One lesson we learned from organizing the visits is that based on the satisfaction survey from follower regions and pilot regions the duration of the visits could have been extended. Certain flexibility within the budget in future projects should ensure to cover enough nights to allow 2 full days site visits. A longer duration of the site visits would have allowed a more detailed introduction of all participants. More opportunities to discuss in detail the regional actions and specificities would have been appreciated by some participants, which would have helped to strengthen the ties between the attendants and boost cooperation on a European scale. However, we would particularly recommend to be flexible on the length of the visits as not all participants have the same amount of time to dedicate to these activities.

What we experienced as vital for the organization of the site visits was that we involved the participants already at an early stage of the development of the programme. This ensured aligned expectations and highly relevant facilities for the on-site visits.

Finally, a key aspect of the fruitful exchange between the participants was the initial twinning exercise, which we performed during the matchmaking process to assign follower regions to the ePLANET pilot regions. This careful selection ensured a good understanding of the participants and triggered the exchange during the site visits and other exchange events.

4 Annexes

4.1 Proposal for joint activities from “D5.7 Follower regions evaluation questionnaire”

Pilot regions	Follower regions	Joint activities
Crete	Municipality of Fyli Macedonia region	Activities: Sharing of experience on SECAP, promotion of Energy Transition Plans. Sharing of experience and best practices on energy communities. Expert visit: Coordination between municipalities and energy manager (Clustering governance - ICAEN)
Girona region	Tâmega e Sousa Baix Llobregat	Activities: Sharing of experience on SECAP and data analysis (EP of buildings and PV-potential). Sharing of experience and best practices on energy communities. Expert visit: Digitalization of SECAP and tools to enhance decision-making on the energy transition (ePLANET platform).
Zlín region	South-East Ireland North-East Bulgaria Bucharest region	Activities: Sharing of experience and best practices on energy communities and related data collection (UC3 and results from the capacity building private webinar). Sharing of experience in data analysis (EP of buildings and PV-potential). Expert visit: Tools for energy monitoring and data management and digitalization of SECAP (ePLANET platform). Energy manager (Clustering governance - ICAEN)

